

SLO-Targeted Congestion Control with Deep Reinforcement Learning

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Abstract—The Internet faces significant challenges in congestion control (CC) due to unpredictable traffic patterns and dynamic network conditions. Traditional CC methods usually struggle to consistently meet strict Service Level Objectives (SLOs) while reducing the end-to-end latency, leading to suboptimal user experiences. In this paper, we introduce DRLLM, a novel congestion control algorithm that seamlessly integrates Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) with the Lagrange Multiplier method. By combining the adaptive intelligence of DRL with the mathematical optimization power of Lagrange multipliers, DRLLM dynamically adjusts to network demands and provides a highly reliable and guaranteed user experience in a variety of network conditions. Our extensive simulations demonstrate superior performance: DRLLM reduces the average latency by 15% compared to BBR, 50% compared to Aurora, and 67% compared to Cubic under high buffer conditions. Moreover, it achieves the lowest latency in 95th percentile across different network conditions with low latency jitter. These results justify DRLLM’s ability to deliver a stable, low-latency and high-throughput performance.

Index Terms—Congestion Control, Deep Reinforcement Learning, Transport Protocol

I. INTRODUCTION

With the explosive growth of wireless devices and data-intensive applications such as streaming media, online gaming, and Internet of Things (IoT), the demand for high-bandwidth and ultra-low-latency communication has significantly increased. These applications impose stringent Service Level Objectives (SLOs), particularly regarding latency and reliability, to ensure a seamless and responsive end-user experience [6].

Traditional TCP Congestion Control Algorithms (CCAs) heavily rely on fixed rules and heuristics to manage congestion and maximize throughput. However, they struggle in dynamic and unpredictable network environments, where packet losses result not only from congestion but also from signal interference, mobility and weak signal strength. Misinterpreting these losses as congestion leads to unnecessary reductions in transmission rates, causing performance degradation and suboptimal throughput. As modern network conditions become increasingly complex and dynamic, existing CCAs fail to consistently maintain low-latency and high reliability which are essential for applications such as real-time video streaming, cloud gaming, and telemedicine.

To tackle these challenges, learning-based Congestion Control (CC) approaches have emerged, leveraging machine learning to adaptively optimize congestion control. While these methods improve responsiveness and throughput, they often overlook explicit SLO constraints, making them unsuitable for latency-sensitive applications [7]. For instance, PCC-Vivace [8] dynamically adjusts sending rates using online learning but primarily focuses on throughput rather than guaranteeing stable low latency. Similarly, Aurora [11] leverages offline learning to optimize sending rates, prioritizing higher throughput but neglecting essential latency constraints. In addition, Orca [1] integrates classical TCP with reinforcement learning-based control. While this approach retains some degree of fairness for TCP, it suffers from unstable convergence and results in inconsistent performance. Overall, existing solutions struggle to deliver a consistent, low-latency performance required by latency-sensitive applications.

A key enabler for latency-sensitive applications is SLO-targeted congestion control. In this work, we propose DRLLM, a novel Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL)-based congestion control algorithm that uses the Lagrange Multiplier method to explicitly enforce latency constraints in its reward function. Lagrange Multiplier efficiently adjusts penalties for SLO violations, achieving stable, efficient and SLO-targeted learning systems. This approach ensures that network latency remains within the predefined SLO thresholds, making it highly effective for latency-sensitive applications. By optimizing end-to-end latency while maintaining competitive throughput, DRLLM outperforms existing learning-based CCAs, providing a more stable and reliable congestion control solution in dynamic network environments.

We summarize our contributions as follows:

- We identify the limitations of existing CCAs, which fall short of reducing the end-to-end latency while meeting explicit Service Level Objectives (SLOs). Existing approaches usually struggle to ensure both low latency and low latency jitter simultaneously, precluding them from being a good fit for latency-sensitive applications.
- We propose DRLLM, a congestion control algorithm that combines Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) and the Lagrange Multiplier method. Using Lagrange Multiplier helps enforce SLO constraints dynamically, reducing the need for extensive reward shaping and improving learn-

ing efficiency. DRLLM dynamically adapts to varying network conditions while enforcing latency constraints, ensuring low latency and low latency jitter with competitive throughput.

- We evaluate DRLLM with extensive simulations in Network Simulator 3 [13] under different network conditions regarding bandwidth, buffer sizes and congestion levels. The results show that DRLLM reduces the average latency by up to 67% compared to existing approaches while yielding excellent network throughput. Additionally, our method achieves the best performance for the 95 percentile of latency and significantly reduces latency jitter, justifying the proposed approach can enforce the SLO guarantee.

II. RELATED WORK

Heuristic-based TCP CCAs, like TCP Reno [16] and Cubic [10], rely on packet loss as a congestion signal, using AIMD (Additive Increase/Multiplicative Decrease) strategies to manage traffic. While effective historically, these methods struggle in modern networks where non-congestion-related losses occur, reducing throughput unnecessarily and leading to increased latency. Consequently, they often fall short of the predictable, low-latency requirements of delay-sensitive applications.

Delay-based CCAs, like TCP Vegas [4], use delay as a signal to detect congestion earlier than packet loss-based methods [16] [10]. However, Vegas struggles with accuracy in dynamic networks where delay may be unrelated to congestion. Hybrid models, such as TCP Compound [17], integrate both delay and packet loss but still face stability issues in varying environments. Newer methods, like Copa [2], attempt to balance latency and throughput using delay and utility maximization principles. BBR [5] models the bottleneck link by measuring the minimum Round-Trip Time (RTT) and bottleneck bandwidth, allowing CC without relying on packet loss or latency monitoring. Nonetheless, these approaches often fall short of providing stable, low latency in highly dynamic networks.

Learning-based CC replaces fixed rule mappings with adaptive strategies. Early approaches like Remy [19] use offline mappings but struggle with dynamic conditions. Modern methods such as PCC-Vivace [8] and Aurora [11] apply online and reinforcement learning to adjust rates based on real-time feedback, improving flexibility. Hybrid models like Orca [1] integrate TCP with reinforcement learning, and Astraea [12] leverages multi-agent learning for better flow interaction management. Spine [18] designs a hierarchical CCA leveraging DRL while keeping overhead extremely low. Owl [14] is a transport protocol leveraging reinforcement learning to optimize congestion window selection based on network signals and end-to-end features, which achieves fair resource allocation after the initial learning. Genet [20] is a curriculum learning-based framework for training RL algorithms that adapt to network environments by progressively incorporating more challenging scenarios, which enhances

training to yield RL policies that provide adaptive streaming, congestion control, and load balancing.

While these learning-based CCAs offer promising approaches to dynamically adapt to time-varying network conditions, they often fall short in consistently achieving low latency with enforced SLO constraints. Most of them are reactive and environment-driven and hence struggle with SLO targets.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT AND SOLUTION

A. Problem Formulation

We define the CC problem within the framework of DRL [9]. In the DRL paradigm, an agent interacts with the environment in a sequential manner, aiming to learn behaviours that maximize cumulative rewards. At each time step t , the agent observes the current state $s_t \in S$ and chooses an action $a_t \in A$ according to its policy $\pi : S \rightarrow A$. Upon executing the action, the agent receives a reward $r_t = r(s_t, a_t)$, and transitions to a new state s_{t+1} . The objective is to find the optimal policy π_θ , parameterized by θ , which maximizes the expected return R_t defined as:

$$R_t = \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \gamma^k r_{t+k} \right], \quad (1)$$

where γ is the discount factor, constrained to the interval $(0, 1)$. γ^k applies a discount based on how far in the future it is, with higher values of k representing rewards further from the present time t . This discount factor enables the model to make decisions that are more favourable in the short term by prioritizing immediate rewards over distant ones. To achieve this objective, DRL employs deep neural networks to approximate the optimal policy π . Specifically, we utilize the PPO algorithm [15] because its primary goal is to find the optimal policy π that maximizes the expected cumulative reward effectively by adjusting the policy iteratively while avoiding large updates.

B. Monitoring Block

The monitoring block is designed to continuously track incoming ACK packets, enabling real-time updates to the DRL agent based on network conditions. The selection of an appropriate monitoring interval is critical. A longer interval can result in an excessively large observation sample, increasing computational complexity and making the data more challenging to process. Additionally, a prolonged interval reduces the frequency of updates, potentially failing to meet the dynamic adjustment requirements of the congestion control algorithm. Conversely, setting the interval too short may not provide sufficient observational data to accurately assess the network state, while also causing frequent adjustments that could destabilize the network. After evaluating various monitoring intervals, we determined that using an interval equivalent to 2 RTTs offers an optimal balance. This interval provides sufficient observation data while minimizing computational overhead, ensuring the CCA remains responsive and lightweight.

C. Action

We decide to determine the optimal sending rate over time as the action. However, the exploration space for sending rate values is huge, making it computationally expensive. Additionally, CC is inherently a real-time problem, requiring fast decisions and quick responses. Unlike many other scenarios, there is no predefined set of action values, and actions must be taken promptly. Consequently, allowing the DRL agent to freely explore this massive action space in search of optimal values within real-time constraints is impractical. To address both the real-time nature of the CC problem and the large action space, we first intelligently reduce the action space. In light of this, we use the sending rate from the last monitor interval (x_{t-1}) as the base sending value to explore a new sending rate (x_t) for the current monitor interval, which means instead of choosing a sending rate directly, DRL-Agent determines a parameter called a_t as the output related to the final sending rate, and α is a scaling factor that helps reduce fluctuations.

$$x_t = \begin{cases} x_{t-1} \cdot (1 + \alpha a_t), & \text{if } a_t \geq 0, \\ x_{t-1} \cdot \frac{1}{1 - \alpha a_t}, & \text{if } a_t < 0, \end{cases}$$

This approach not only significantly reduces the model's convergence time but also ensures effective fine-grained adjustments to the sending rate.

D. State

To meet our goals of providing guaranteed, stable latency while maintaining relatively good throughput, we collect several key statistics. These include (1) the latency gradient, representing the increase in latency over consecutive intervals, (2) the ratio of current latency to the minimum latency observed since the start of the connection, and (3) the send ratio, defined as the ratio of the received rate to the send rate.

E. Reward

The design of the reward function is crucial in regulating the variation of the sending rate, as different applications have distinct requirements for network parameters such as bandwidth, latency, throughput, and packet loss.

Inspired by Aurora's reward function [11], we devise our reward function to ensure low and guaranteed latency. By incorporating a latency constraint into the reward function, our model strikes a nice balance between system throughput with guaranteed low latency. In other words, our problem is maximizing the reward with strict latency constraints. This approach allows the model to better serve latency-sensitive applications by ensuring it prioritizes actions that maintain latency within acceptable limits, while still optimizing overall network performance.

Converting constrained optimization problems into unconstrained ones is a crucial technique in optimization theory. The advantage of this transformation is that it allows the use of powerful unconstrained optimization methods, which are often easier to implement and more computationally efficient.

To achieve this transformation, we have adopted the Lagrange multiplier method [3]. This approach introduces additional variables, known as Lagrange multipliers, to incorporate the constraints into the objective function. By doing so, the original problem is converted to an unconstrained optimization problem, where the gradients of the objective function and the constraints are aligned at the solution point. This method provides a systematic way to handle both equality and inequality constraints, making it an essential tool in solving complex optimization problems across various fields. In our work, we specifically deal with an inequality constraint, as the latency must be kept below a predefined threshold.

Adding a Constraint to our Reward Function with Lagrange multiplier method

We have an optimization problem to maximize an objective function $f(x)$ subject to an inequality constraint $g(x) < 0$, where x is the vector of decision variables. The Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) conditions can be used to extend the Lagrange multiplier method by introducing additional conditions. The corresponding Lagrangian function can be defined as:

$$L(x, \lambda) = f(x) + \lambda g(x), \quad (2)$$

Here, λ is the Lagrange multiplier, which represents the sensitivity of the objective function to the constraint $g(x)$. The optimization problem is then transformed into finding the saddle points of the Lagrangian by solving the following system of equations:

$$\nabla_x L(x, \lambda) = \nabla f(x) + \lambda \nabla g(x) = 0,$$

$$g(x) < 0,$$

The first condition ensures that the gradient of the objective function, adjusted by the constraint, is zero, indicating a potential extremum. The second condition ensures that the constraint is satisfied.

For problems involving multiple constraints, say m equality constraints $g_i(x) = 0$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$, the Lagrangian generalizes to:

$$L(x, \lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_m) = f(x) + \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i g_i(x), \quad (3)$$

In this case, each λ_i is a Lagrange multiplier associated with the corresponding constraint $g_i(x) < 0$.

For each inequality constraint, a multiplier λ_i is associated, and the system of equations becomes:

$$\nabla_x L(x, \lambda) = \nabla f(x) + \sum \lambda_i \nabla g_i(x) = 0,$$

$$g_i(x) \leq 0,$$

$$\lambda_i \geq 0,$$

Dynamic Optimization of Lagrange Multipliers

In optimization problems involving inequality constraints $g_i(x)$, it is crucial to dynamically adjust the Lagrange multipliers λ_i . Specifically, when the value of the constraint $g_i(x)$ increases, the corresponding Lagrange multiplier λ_i should also increase. Conversely, when $g_i(x)$ decreases, λ_i should be reduced. This adaptive adjustment can be achieved by introducing a learning mechanism that dynamically updates λ_i based on the state of the constraint $g_i(x)$.

Incremental Update Method

A simple incremental update method can be utilized to adjust λ_i by calculating the change in the constraint value. Given the current value of λ_i as $\lambda_i(t)$, the update rule can be defined as follows:

$$\lambda_{i(t+1)} = \lambda_{i(t)} + \alpha \cdot \frac{g_i(x)_t - g_i(x)_{t-1}}{g_i(x)_t}, \quad (4)$$

where:

- α is the learning rate, which controls the step size of the update.
- $g_i(x)_t$ represents the constraint value at the current time step.
- $g_i(x)_{t-1}$ is the constraint value at the previous time step.

Ensuring Non-negativity

Since λ_i must remain non-negative as it represents a Lagrange multiplier, it is essential to ensure this condition is satisfied during the updating process. Thus, after the update, we apply the following correction:

$$\lambda_{i(t+1)} = \max(0, \lambda_{i(t+1)}), \quad (5)$$

Final Reward function

Based on the analysis above, we propose the following final reward function,

$$\text{Reward} = 10 \times thr - 1000 \times lat - 2000 \times loss - \lambda(lat - thr_lat). \quad (6)$$

where thr represents throughput(in packets per second), lat is latency(in seconds), $loss$ is the packet loss rate (proportion of packets not acknowledged), thr_lat is the target latency threshold, and λ is the dynamic Lagrange multiplier. The factors in the reward function (e.g., 10, 1000, 2000) are set based on the magnitude of each component to ensure that the reward stays within a reasonable range. This scaling prevents any individual factor from dominating the overall reward calculation and ensures balanced optimization. Specifically, the units of throughput, latency, and packet loss differ significantly, so these multipliers are introduced to normalize their effects, allowing the function to reflect meaningful trade-offs between performance metrics without skewing the model toward one metric excessively. This final reward function captures the trade-off between throughput, latency, and loss while enforcing a latency constraint through $\lambda(lat - thr_lat)$, ensuring optimal performance for latency-sensitive applications.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

A. Experimental Setup

Simulation Environment We conduct our experiments on a server with 4 CPU cores and 4GB memory. To evaluate the performance and robustness of the trained model, we conducted extensive experiments using the Network Simulator 3 (NS3) [13]. The experimental scenario is a single flow on a link whose capacity alternates between 10 Mbps and 30 Mbps every 15 seconds.

B. Performance Benchmarks

We selected three state-of-the-art algorithms as benchmarks: BBR and Cubic, widely adopted and well-recognized conventional congestion control algorithms, and Aurora, a highly regarded open-source RL-based algorithm. This selection includes both traditional and learning-based approaches.

- 1) **BBR** [5] estimates bottleneck bandwidth and RTT to control the sending rate.
- 2) **Cubic** [10] uses a cubic growth function for congestion window adjustment.
- 3) **Aurora** [11] applies deep reinforcement learning to dynamically adjust the sending rate without incorporating any SLO constraints.

C. System Throughput

Fig. 1: Throughput Under Dynamically Changing Bandwidth

TABLE I: MSE Analysis of Algorithms Against Theoretical Optimal Value

Algorithm	Mean Square Error (MSE)
Aurora	21.26
BBR	16.77
Cubic	12.26
DRLLM	18.37

To simulate time-varying network link conditions, such as those commonly observed in wireless networks, satellite communications, or congested WAN links, we evaluate our

proposed method under dynamically changing bandwidth conditions to assess its ability to adapt quickly and accurately to varying link capacities. In particular, we designed a scenario where the bandwidth changes every 15 seconds to ensure enough time for CCAs to converge and fit the path change intervals of flows. Initially, the bandwidth is set to 20 Mbps, increasing to 30 Mbps after 15 seconds, and then decreasing by 10 Mbps every 15 seconds. The simulation runs for a total of 60 seconds, with the final bandwidth reduced to 10 Mbps.

As shown in Figure 1, the proposed method (DRLLM) adapts rapidly to changes in bandwidth, closely tracking available link capacity for most of the evaluation period. Although the throughput exhibits more significant fluctuations compared to TCP Cubic, it performs more consistently than BBR. Specifically, our method shows a slight advantage over BBR, as it avoids the abrupt drops in throughput that BBR tends to experience. We also calculated the Mean Square Error (MSE) to assess the average squared deviation between ideal and actual throughput, with lower values indicating closer alignment with link capacity. As seen in Table I, our method achieves a relatively low MSE (18.37) compared to Aurora, though Cubic (12.26) and BBR (16.67) perform slightly better. This indicates that while our approach is comparable in maintaining optimal throughput.

D. Latency

Fig. 2: Average latency under different buffer queue size

To evaluate whether our proposed method can effectively handle various router queue buffer sizes, we conducted a series of experiments with buffer sizes ranging from 75 to 1500 packets. Given that our bottleneck bandwidth in this experiment is 20 Mbps and the base delay of the bottleneck link is 30 ms, with a default packet size of 1024 bytes, the bandwidth-delay product (BDP) equates to 75 packets. The goal is to assess the sensitivity of our proposed method to different buffer queue sizes, allowing us to understand its adaptability across varying network conditions.

From Figure 2, it is evident that the Cubic congestion control algorithm exhibits increasing latency with the increment of buffer queue size. Specifically, when the buffer size reaches 200 packets, the latency observed is more than double that at 75 packets. As the buffer expands further to 1500 packets, latency becomes critically high, approaching 600 ms. This phenomenon occurs because Cubic’s aggressive nature leads to a rapid increase in the congestion window, which, when paired with larger buffers, results in higher queuing delays as packets accumulate in the queue. The algorithm’s tendency to fill the buffer can exacerbate latency, particularly when experiencing high traffic demand, as the increased queue length directly correlates to longer wait times for packets to be transmitted.

In contrast, our proposed method maintains a relatively stable average latency as the buffer queue size increases. Notably, with a queue buffer size as high as 1500 packets, our method maintains an average latency of approximately 34 ms, comparable to the latency observed at 75 packets. This stability underscores the robustness of our approach to managing latency effectively under varying buffer conditions. Furthermore, it outperforms Aurora and BBR in terms of latency, achieving half the latency of Aurora and reducing latency by 15% compared to BBR, which means our proposed method can deliver a much lower delay under the same conditions.

E. CDF of Latency and Latency Jitter

Fig. 3: CDF of Latency

The experimental setup for this evaluation is identical to that described in the previous section on Dynamic Bandwidth. This setup includes varying bandwidth conditions to simulate a dynamic network environment, which provides a test for assessing the method’s ability to maintain latency stability. By conducting the experiment under these fluctuating bandwidth conditions, we aim to demonstrate the robustness of the proposed method in achieving stable latency even when network bandwidth is subject to change.

Fig. 4: Latency Jitter

The evaluation results demonstrate that the proposed method successfully maintains latency within the desired threshold, achieving guaranteed latency performance. Notably, 98% of all measured latencies remained below the predefined threshold (45ms), indicating the robustness of the method under various network conditions. This consistent performance showcases the method’s effectiveness in controlling latency, thereby ensuring a stable and responsive network environment that meets predefined latency requirements.

In comparison to Cubic, BBR, and Aurora, from the results of CDF (Cumulative Distribution Function) shown in Figure 3, our proposed method demonstrates superior latency performance, achieving the lowest latency at the 95th percentile. The results for latency jitter, as illustrated in Figure 4, show that our proposed method consistently achieves significantly lower jitter compared to both Aurora and Cubic, while BBR generally offers similar levels of latency jitter.

These results demonstrate the robustness of our proposed method in maintaining guaranteed low latency and stable jitter under various conditions, supporting latency-sensitive applications.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we propose DRLLM, an end-to-end congestion control algorithm that provides low and SLO-targeted latency. DRLLM combines deep reinforcement learning with the Lagrange Multiplier method, optimizing performance with enforced SLO constraints. This combination allows the deep reinforcement learning model to efficiently learn strategies within specific thresholds, providing stable and SLO-targeted performance. Extensive simulations demonstrate superior performance: DRLLM reduces the average latency by 15%, 50% and 67% compared to BBR, Aurora and Cubic, respectively. Moreover, we achieve the lowest latency in the 95th percentile across different network conditions while maintaining the lowest latency jitter among all compared methods.

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